

GENDER BIOGRAPHY, AS A WAY OF FORMING GENDER IDENTITY

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Abstract. *In modern psychology, the gender direction is actively developing. However, there are a number of fundamental problems in determining the theoretical and methodological foundations of gender psychology. The following thesis presents the origins of gender psychology, the widespread use of the concept of gender, and the deep penetration of the concept of gender into the lifestyle of society.*

Keywords: *liberal feminism, gender identity, stereotype, Gender studies, gender difference, deconstruction, Patriarchy, category.*

**GENDER BIOGRAFIYASI, GENDER IDINDEFIKATORLIK SHAKILLANISH
USLUBI SIFATIDA**

Annotatsiya. *Zamonaviy psixologiya fanida gender yo'nalishi faol o'rganilib rivojlanmoqda. Biroq, gender psixologiyasining nazariy va uslubiy asoslarini belgilashda bir qator fundamental muammolar mavjud. Quyidagi tadqiqotimizda gender psixologiyaning kelib chiqishi, gender tushinchasining keng tarqalishi va jamiyat turmush tarzida gender tushunchasining chuqur singishi keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *liberal feminism, jinslarning o'xshashli, stereotip, Gendershunolik, jinslar farqi, dekonstruksiya, Patriarxat, kategoriya.*

**GENDER BIOGRAFIYASI GENDER ITINDEFIKATORLIQ QALIPLESIW
PROCESININ METODI SIPATIDA**

Annotatsiya. *Zamanagóy psixologiya páninde gender baǵdari aktiv úyrenilip rawajlanıp atır. Biraq, gender psixologiyasınıń teoriyalıq hám metodikalıq tiykarların belgilewde bir qatar fundamental máseleler bar. Tómendegi tezisiimizda gender psixologiyasınıń kelip shıǵıwı, gender túsiniginiń keń tarqalıwı hám jámiyet turmıs tarızinde gender túsiniginiń tereń sińiwi keltirilgen.*

Gilt sözler: Liberal feminism, jinslardıñ uqsash, stereotip, gendershunashlıq, jinslar parqı, dekonstruksiya, Patriarxat, kategoriya.

Introduction

In the development of gender studies in the West, three stages can be conditionally distinguished. The first stage (approximate time limits of the 60s-70s) is the period of the emergence of the first gender-oriented scientific works, associated with the rapid development of the liberal-oriented feminist movement in the West.

If we consider the example of a family, then it is necessary to distinguish functions: a woman performs an expressive function (establishing internal balance in the family), and a man performs an instrumental function (regulating relations between the family and other social structures). Liberal feminists, understanding the position of women within the framework of Parsonism, formulated the thesis about the oppression of women and men by the traditional roles assigned to them, and set themselves the political task of changing these roles into action. They aimed to "break" stereotypes in the public consciousness (which associated women only with education, care and service, and men with management) through a broad program of social changes in the educational system, production, political and legislative spheres, through the provision of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in society.

The second stage of the development of gender studies falls on the first half of the 80s.

At that time, radical feminism was widespread. If liberal feminism solved the dilemma of "similarity - gender difference" through the similarity, uniformity of men and women, then radical feminism built its theory and practice on the differences between men and women. The ideology of radical feminism was aimed at oppression and discrimination against women. The beginning of the third stage of the development of gender studies is associated with the second half of the 80s.

The feminist movement of this period is characterized by multi-disciplinary nature: color feminism, postmodernism, humanistic, existential, cultural feminism, etc. The task of the new forces of feminist ideas in the late 1980s became to clarify the foundations (deconstructions) of gender relations. The transition from the analysis of patriarchy to the analysis of the factors determining the formation of the gender system and gender begins. The division of people into men and women determines the perception of differences inherent in the human psyche and behavior (Bern, 2001). Many believe that these differences are associated with the genetic, anatomical and physiological characteristics of the male and female organism.

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The idea of the opposition of the principles of masculinity and femininity is found in the myths and traditions of all known societies. It is entrenched in various social institutions (family, army, educational institutions, judicial bodies). The emergence of the term "gender" as one of the categories of social analysis is associated with the name of the American psychoanalyst Robert Stoller, who in 1958 proposed the use of this grammatical category to emphasize the dual nature of human. In everyday speech, the word "gender" refers to a wide range of reproductive, somatic, behavioral and social characteristics that characterize a person as male or female.

The term "gender" was intended to emphasize that biological characteristics are not directly given to a person, but are always refracted through the prism of individual consciousness and social representations, that is, they exist in the form of subjective and culturally reinforced knowledge about them (Stoller, 1968). Gender is a set of specific cultural characteristics that determine the social behavior of women and men and their relationships with each other.

Like the concepts of class, race and ethnicity, the concept of gender is an analytical tool for understanding social processes. The main stages of the development of gender studies in psychology can be briefly described as follows (Ivanova, 2001). Initially, they were conducted within the framework of the study of individual differences, masculinity and femininity were measured like other individual differences.

Then they tried to understand them as the most important characteristics of the personality, and the family was considered as an environment where the socialization of boys and girls takes place and they assume social roles based on established cultural stereotypes. In the 1970s, S. Bem, who introduced the concept of "androgyny" (meaning a successful combination of traditionally male and female psychological qualities) and developed the corresponding methodological apparatus, was able to empirically demonstrate that masculinity and femininity are two independent, but not contradictory, constructs.

The development of gender sociology as a more or less clearly defined subject of scientific knowledge is associated with the second half of the 20th century (60s-70s). Until this period, one can only speak of the necessary conditions for the development of gender sociology.

An analysis of literary sources on the history of the development of gender sociology allows us to identify two stages:

1) the necessary conditions for the development of gender sociology (late 19th - mid-20th centuries);

2) the formation and development of gender sociology - the second half of the 20th century.

For the analysis of gender relations, work on such subjects of gender sociology as the

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differentiation of male and female roles in society and the family, the relationship between the professional and family roles of men and women, social stereotypes of "masculinity" and "femininity" and their influence on various aspects of the social behavior of men and women is of great importance.

Conclusion

Currently, the world is at the peak of the era of the primacy of rights, the value of human life, and the primacy of humanity. Among these issues, a lot of research has been done on the issue of gender equality. In recent years, the concept of gender has played a major role in achieving gender equality and eliminating inequality between men and women in society.

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